
Coping With the Challenges in Teaching MAPEH Subjects among Non-specialized Teachers of Division of Davao Del Sur

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ABSTRACT: Given the current state of the educational system, only some educators teach outside their field of expertise, which causes difficulties and stresses in the subjects they teach. This descriptive-comparative research examined the coping mechanisms and performance of 150 non-specialized MAPEH teachers in Davao del Sur. One standardized questionnaire from Montesur (2021) was utilized to collect data computed using the mean and KruskalWallis test to determine the coping mechanisms and performance of the non-specialized MAPEH teachers and assess their differences concerning their profile. The findings showed a very high level of coping mechanisms and performance as they teach MAPEH subjects. Furthermore, there is no significant difference between their coping mechanisms and performance as analyzed in terms of gender, educational attainment, age, years in service, and specializations. This implied that non-specialized MAPEH teachers managed the subjects well and performed excellently despite not specializing in the course. Thus, the researchers recommended that future researchers conduct an in-depth understanding of the experiences of these out-of-field teachers and the viewpoints of students under their tutelage.

KEYWORDS: coping mechanisms, performance, quantitative-descriptive, non-specialized MAPEH teachers, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Given the status of the educational system today, educators often teach subjects that have nothing to do with their line of work or the subjects they studied for their college degrees. As a result, teachers need help teaching the course and dealing with the stresses and challenges of this misalignment (Campbell et al., 2021). According to Hershock (2023), to teach with assurance and efficacy, instructors must be knowledgeable about the topic and competent in comprehending and putting into practice a well-structured curriculum in the classroom. They must possess sufficient teaching and learning experiences for the prescribed course because Co, Abella, De Jesus (2021) and Campbell et al. (2021) posit that higher student accomplishment is affected by subject-specific knowledge from the teachers and their subject competence. Cohen, Ruzek, and Sandilos (2018) contend that a teacher who does not specialize in the subject he teaches or who possesses content knowledge does not achieve sufficient education. Because of this instructional mismatch, educators who teach in a field irrelevant to their field of expertise suffer from coping with the challenges brought by this educative circumstance (Condie et al., 2019).

To teach a subject means to have enough knowledge of it (Ferlazzo, 2018).

However, this is different in some secondary schools and universities in the United States. Due to instructors' lack of skill and enthusiasm due to teaching misalignment, American students frequently express their discontent with the quality of instruction they get in their classrooms (Cohen & Goldhaber, 2018). Moreover, teachers reteach and revisit the subjects they have already covered (Nixon et al., 2019; Mizzi, 2018) because the prevalence of subject mismatch has led to low student academic progress and poor learning experiences when they are promoted to the following year level (Cohen, 2018; Childs & McNicholl, 2018). Similarly, in a study conducted in Malaysia, Ghani, Ahmad, and Ibrahim (2014), as cited by Zhou (2018), discovered that in addition to the harmful effects of misalignment on the students, teachers who are new to the subject they are teaching are frequently mock by their pupils and later, experience mild stress and pressures. Numerous teachers in Australia experience everyday frustration because they are unfamiliar with the subject loads and eventually resort to resignation (Hobbs et al., 2022).

In the Philippines, mismatched teaching loads are very popular. Because of misaligned instructors, particularly in elementary, the quality of teachers in the Philippine educational system has become one of the most discussed topics over time (Co et al., 2022). According to Bilasa (2019) and Buedron (2018), such a trend violates the Department of Education policy outlined in DO 13, s. 1994 -Guidelines for Matching Specialization in Teaching Preparation with Teaching Assignments for Public School Teachers. Notably, during the opening of Senior High School education, Ocampo (2018) explains, as cited by Datingaling (2019), that the lack of preparation forces some Filipino teachers to teach subjects irrelevant to their field, which is why Samillano (2019) argues that many senior high school

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graduates who proceed to college remain incompetent on their majors due to insufficient learning experience. Such mismatch has also led to knowledge gaps and inadequate teachings modified in the latter years of their education (Querubin, 2020; Orlando, 2018). This situation needs to improve the country's education quality, causing poor student learning and demotivating Filipino teachers (Guiaselon et al., 2022; Mangubos, 2019; Caylao, 2017).

Mindanao is also guilty of this problem. In Digos City, teachers, especially in MAPEH, receive subject loads outside their fields of specialization and, hence, are perceived to be less effective in content delivery. Aside from affecting students' performance, this misalignment triples teachers' burden and stress in the academe because, as non-specialists in the field, they find it challenging to teach the competencies due to a deficit of background and exposure in the course. In this context, the researchers pursue this research to examine the coping mechanisms and performance of nonspecialized MAPEH teachers in Davao del Sur.

Furthermore, this study dealt with non-specialized teachers' difficulties when instructing MAPEH. To comprehend their strategies for coping and prospects for achievement, the researchers draw upon Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, particularly his notion of teaching efficacy. According to Bandura, teaching efficacy is related to a teacher's conviction that they can influence students' learning meaningfully (Barni et al., 2018; Bandura, 1977). Caylao (2017) asserted that instructional efficacy includes controlling students' motivation and interest in a variety of activities as well as using tailored teaching and classroom management techniques to address misbehavior from students (such as poor engagement and lack of interest). In the context of this research, Bandura's theory of teaching efficacy provides a valuable lens through which to analyze non-specialized MAPEH teachers' experiences, enhancing the educational experience for students in the broad field of MAPEH. This framework provided insights into how non-specialized instructors' perceptions of their talents affect their performance, resilience, and engagement in managing the demands of MAPEH.

Additionally, the findings of this study will benefit the Department of Education by realizing the role of professional alignment in teachers' teaching experiences; this could provide empirical input into how subject loads work in some schools in the Philippines and how it hampers teachers' performance and health as well as student's academic wellbeing. UM Digos College may benefit from the results for the academe to be informed about how the mismatch of subjects and teachers influences their work and students' progress and achievement. For non-specialized teachers, especially those elementary teachers who will be primarily exposed to different subjects in their actual teaching practice, the results can instill in them some effective coping mechanisms used by their co-teachers when faced with stresses and challenges due to teaching mismatched courses. Lastly, for future researchers, the findings serve as literature support to expand the knowledge obtained from this study. Since this is a timely educational concern, the study can be used as a reference to investigate relevant concerns of subject mismatch and teacher misalignment.

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study examined non-specialized teachers' coping mechanisms and performance in teaching MAPEH subjects in Davao del Sur. Specifically, this sought to achieve the following:

- 1) To determine the demographic profile of the non-specialized MAPEH teachers in terms of;
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 years in service;
 - 1.4 educational attainment;
 - 1.5 specialization.

- 2) To examine the coping mechanisms of the non-specialized MAPEH teachers in terms of;
 - 2.1 time management;
 - 2.2 academic advice and mentoring;
 - 2.3 appraisal focused;
 - 2.4 emotion-focused; and 2.5 occupation-focused coping.

- 3) To ascertain the performance of the non-specialized MAPEH teachers in terms of;
 - 3.1 classroom management;
 - 3.2 coaching and training; and
 - 3.3 handling ancillary tasks.

- 4) To assess the significant difference in the coping mechanisms and performance of non-specialized MAPEH teachers when analysed by profile.

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3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study was quantitative and utilized descriptive-comparative research design because the researchers aimed to describe the coping mechanisms and performance of the nonspecialized teachers teaching MAPEH subjects in the Davao del Sur Division and examine if a significant difference exists when analyzed by profile. According to Arnold (2019), the descriptive-comparative method describes and compares the existence of a phenomenon or situation. Parallel to this, the design helped researchers examine how non-specialized instructors performed and coped with the challenges of teaching MAPEH unrelated to their profession, considering their age, gender, years in service, educational attainment, and specialization.

3.2 Research Participants

One hundred fifty (150) non-specialized teachers from Davao del Sur participated in the study. The respondents conformed to the desired criteria provided by the researcher to qualify for participation. This included: 1) non-specialized teachers were currently teaching MAPEH subjects; 2) They must be elementary teachers teaching in schools in Davao del Sur. Moreover, in selecting the respondents, the researchers also adhered to the purposive sampling technique to ensure their qualifications in answering the survey and the accuracy and reliability of the data collected to generate results. As Aguinardo (2021) explained, purposive sampling helps researchers access a specific group of persons suitable for a given profile. Therefore, in this study, the researchers relied on the participation of the participants based on whom they selected who were suitable for giving the responses required.

Additionally, the respondents' consent was essential before the survey questionnaires. Furthermore, they received a thorough explanation of the ramifications and risks associated with their participation. To guarantee that no threat, intimidation, coercion, or compulsion was used against them if they decided to withdraw from the research, they were granted free will and voluntariness to decide on their own. Their comments were neither disclosed nor made public without consent, and they received stringent confidentiality treatment.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Presented in Table 1 are the data that summarize the demographic profile, namely age, gender, years in service, educational attainment, and field of specialization graduated of the 150 nonspecialized teachers from Davao del Sur who are currently teaching MAPEH subjects. There were 80 (53.3%) teachers whose ages fell to the threshold of 35- 44 years old, followed by 34 (22.7%) teachers who were already 25-34 years old. 22 (14.7%) were between 45 and 54 years old, and only 14 (9.3%) teachers were 55-64. Regarding gender, female teachers took the lead with a total of 122 (81.3%), far behind the 28 (18.7%) male teachers. Moreover, as for their years in service, 82 (54.7%) teachers have been practicing the teaching profession for ten years and above. 45 (30%) teachers have been teaching for 6-10 years, while 23 (15.3%) have been immersed in the field for 1-5 years. About their educational attainment, 111 (74%) teachers already had their bachelor's degree, while the remaining 39 (26%) had already finished their master's degree. Lastly, for their field of specialization, most of the teachers were BEED graduates, with a total of 115 (76.7%). There were 13 (8.7%) teachers who specialized in Mathematics and English respectively in their undergraduate years. Of 150, only 5 (3.3%) teachers pursued BSED- Filipino, whereas 4 (2.7%) were science majors.

Table 1. Demographic profile of respondents, n=150

	<i>f</i>	%
Age		
25-34	34	22.7
35-44	80	53.3
45-54	22	14.7
55-64	14	9.3
Gender		
Male	28	18.7
Female	122	81.3
Years in Service		
1-5 years	23	15.3
6-10 years	45	30
Ten years above	82	54.7

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Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	111	74
Master's Degree	39	26
of Specialization Graduated BEED		
	115	76.7
English	13	8.7
Math	13	8.7
Filipino	5	3.3
Science	4	2.7

Level of Coping Mechanisms of the Non-Specialized MAPEH Teachers

Table 2. Level of coping mechanisms of the non-specialized MAPEH teachers, $n=150$ \bar{x} SD

Time Management	3.61	0.48
Academic Advice and Mentoring	3.25	0.57
Appraisal Focused	3.28	0.56
Emotion Focused	2.91	0.67
Occupation Focused	3.09	0.62
Overall	3.22	0.44

Table 2 shows the level of coping mechanisms as analyzed according to time management, academic advice and mentoring, appraisal-focused, emotion-focused, and occupation-focused of the 150 non-specialized MAPEH teachers in Davao del Sur. Overall, the coping mechanisms of the 150 non-specialized MAPEH teachers obtained a mean of 3.22 (SD=0.44), which means moderate, implying that the coping mechanisms of nonspecialized teachers in Davao del Sur are sometimes observed in teaching MAPEH subjects. Despite not majoring in this course, they employed various coping methods to handle the stress and complexity of teaching the components of the subject matter. The instructors know stress management's value and are trying to accomplish their respective roles and responsibilities in the teaching profession.

This result is consistent with Montesur (2021), who stated that those teachers who teach subjects not aligned with their field have well-composed adaptive strategies. Since they most likely forecast the difficulty they might encounter along the way, they set beforehand the Possible mechanisms they can employ to cope with the challenges (Mangubos, 2019). Their mind is already prepared for any upcoming complications. Bala (2017) discussed the factors that influence misaligned instructors' success, notwithstanding the challenges and pressures of the subjects they instruct. Among them is passion, which helps them navigate the multiple challenges of instructing a subject they could be more knowledgeable about. Similarly, Biesta (2019) asserted that enthusiastic, generalist teachers are prepared for many knocking possibilities that arise. Their passion makes them flexible and dynamic in the teaching profession despite the stresses that are tripled along the way (Querubin, 2020; Waltz, 2016).

Additionally, Flores (2019) highlighted that teachers who do not major in MAPEH but are currently teaching the subject exhibited their willingness to learn and go outside their shells. As educators, they are open to new learning opportunities that let them practice and teach what they are passionate about (Subon & Sigie, 2018; Zhou, 2018; Ghani et al., 2014). According to Hobbs (2022), participating in professional development workshops in the course or speaking with other educators who are experienced and experts in the teaching industry is beneficial enough to complement the professional competence of MAPEH majors already working in the field and help them better and much more effective nonspecialized MAPEH teachers. In Table 2, the level of coping mechanisms of the nonspecialized MAPEH teachers' time management is the leading coping mechanism present among non-specialized MAPEH teachers since it acquired a mean of 3.61 (SD= 0.48). This signifies that non-specialized teachers' coping mechanisms regarding time management in Davao del Sur are frequently observed when teaching MAPEH subjects. The itemized results indicated that they always set the goals they want to achieve in their discussion and ready the lessons in every component of the subject matter to make it aligned with the course and fit with what the students expect to experience. Most importantly, these nonspecialized MAPEH teachers make the most of the lesson's limited time to cover all the topics before examination or summative assessments.

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This finding supports Zhou's postulation (2018), underscoring that time management is crucial for many instructors to divide their heavy workloads into smaller, more manageable tasks. According to Campbell et al. (2021), time management is a strategy that can help instructors feel less overwhelmed and stay on task despite the flurry of obligations that come with their various jobs. Similarly, when they effectively manage their time, they are more likely to achieve the objectives they set for themselves and teaching, giving them more chances to prepare their lectures in advance, make the most of their classroom time, and avoid feeling rushed (Buedron, 2018; Caylao, 2017). Condie, Lefgren, and Sims (2019) also found that time management is the most significant defense for non-specialized teachers to guarantee that all topics in their subjects are addressed equitably. Non-specialized instructors might have the propensity to concentrate on their favorite courses or the subjects they feel most at ease instructing, but with good time management skills, they can ensure that all subjects receive the same amount of attention (Co et al., 2021; Childs & McNicholl, 2018). Furthermore, this means of coping works well for preventing overload. Time management is essential for teachers to feel more in control of their workload and reduce stress, as well as to become more efficient and have more time for their personal lives (Guiaselon et al., 2022). Datingaling (2019) explained that teaching subjects that need to be better or aligned with one's expertise can be overwhelming. With proper usage and allotment of time, teachers can minimize feeling such.

As for appraisal focused, Table 2 disclosed its mean of 3.28 (SD=0.56), indicating moderate, suggesting that the coping mechanisms for appraisal focused for nonspecialized teachers are sometimes observed in teaching MAPEH subjects. The itemized results revealed that when faced with classroom issues, non-specialist MAPEH instructors in Davao del Sur showed decision-making abilities and made the most of their time before teaching to speak and consult with their co-teachers. Additionally, they know when to react in a classroom situation, especially when a student's worries come up, and they use a variety of teaching techniques to capture students' interest and attention, including using humor or jokes without deviating from the topics being covered.

Nixon, Luft, and Ross (2019) posited that teachers can benefit significantly from an appraisal-focused coping strategy since it enables them to focus on the good parts of a situation, even when it is difficult. Such a mechanism motivates them to advance regardless of how thick the route may be since they frequently confront several problems, including teaching numerous courses, covering a wide range of topics, and fulfilling the needs of diverse learners (Mizzi, 2018). On top of that, Mangubos (2019) underlined that non-specialized instructors are less likely to feel stressed and overwhelmed when they concentrate on the favorable aspects of their employment, maintaining a positive attitude about their work even when dealing with difficulties. Non-specialized educators who can handle stress and difficulties well are likelier to give their pupils engaging and effective teaching. According to Condie, Lefgren, and Sims (2019) and Guiaselon et al. (2022), this may result in better student results. Likewise, Hobbs (2022) claimed that an appraisal focused coping mechanism helps teachers stay motivated and engaged in their work, even when stressed and faced with various problems in their subject matters. Guiaselon et al. (2022) recommended that they take the time to celebrate their successes, no matter how small they may appear, so that their perspective toward their work remains strong. More so, Datingaling (2019) argued that they must contact their colleagues, mentors, and other support networks for consultation and professional guidance to feel less alone, develop new coping mechanisms, and make the best decision.

Table 2 also revealed academic advice and mentoring as coping mechanisms for non-specialized MAPEH teachers in Davao del Sur. As shown, it garnered a mean of 3.25 (SD=0.57), which means moderate, implying that the coping mechanisms regarding academic advice and mentoring of non-specialized teachers are sometimes observed in teaching MAPEH subjects. This result was justified in their itemized responses when participating teachers admitted that they received any mentorship or help from their heads or more knowledgeable and experienced MAPEH colleagues, specifically with content and pedagogical concerns. They were open to asking for it in the first place since they thought it was for their own, which would benefit their students in the teaching process. Because of such circumstances, they consistently showed a high likelihood of working with them and sharing ideas with their co-MAPEH teachers.

This result is tangent with the scholarly claims of Montesur (2021), who highlighted the necessity for academic advice and mentoring in the academic space, especially for those teachers who do not specialize in the subjects under their loads. He contested that the high academic advice and mentorship that non-specialized MAPEH teachers received in District 4 of Laguna helped them in several ways, particularly in easing the difficulty of teaching the subject and ensuring that the appropriate teaching pedagogies were applied to each MAPEH component. More so, Van den Brande et al. (2019) asserted that academic mentorship is vital for non-specialized instructors because, in the first place, MAPEH is not their field of expertise. It is a small part of pursuing the grueling battle in their respective majors. Being able to receive help from trained professionals on the subject helps, or at least minimizes, their work stress by receiving expert advice on handling the class much better based on proven experiences (Biesta, 2019; Bala, 2017).

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Furthermore, Thi and Truong (2020) affirmed that non-specialized instructors must see subject knowledge as essential for teaching effectiveness due to a lack of specialization, insufficient training, and awareness of the several techniques and tactics ideal for teaching MAPEH. The teacher's efforts alone could not be enough to achieve it. Academic mentoring from their superiors is required to develop new subject-matter skills and knowledge, cultivate teaching strategies appropriate for the course, gain confidence in their subject-matter expertise, and, most importantly, lessen stress (Querubin, 2020; Samillano, 2019; Orlando, 2018). Zhou (2018) claimed that mentoring enables non-specialized MAPEH teachers to get constructive criticism on improving their lesson plans and teaching techniques. Weldon (2020) further stated that it is the ideal method for fostering a culture of cooperation and camaraderie in the academic setting, especially in the face of stress and course challenges.

As for occupation-focused, it took the mean of 3.09 (SD = 0.62), which indicates moderate, with the implication that the coping mechanisms in terms of occupation-focused for non-specialized teachers are sometimes observed in teaching MAPEH subjects. This suggests that non-specialized MAPEH teachers can often use their work to cope with the different forms of burden and tasks of teaching the course. This result also correlated with their itemized responses, where teachers acknowledged their ability to work independently and their increased confidence in teaching the subject matter because of the advice and mentorship they received from expert MAPEH teachers. Furthermore, they also admitted their competence in sharing positive influence and regard for the subject since they exuded a hopeful outlook on the subject matter they taught. Because of this setup, their students become so interested and more engaged that teachers are satisfied with their outputs every time they submit their outputs.

This finding parallels Montesor (2021), who revealed that non-specialized teachers in District 4 Laguna positively work on their own and with their colleagues to provide the best learning environment for their students. Despite the mismatch of the subject they teach to their respective majors, they use their strengths as an advantage in teaching the subject despite its complexity. They also solicit help and support from their co-MAPEH teachers so that they can teach the course much better and rise from the different forms of stress that the subject matter renders (Chen et al., 2017). However, Darling-Hammond, Furger, Shields, and Sutchter (2019) provided a different lens, arguing that non-specialized teachers face many challenges in teaching subjects they need to be more knowledgeable of. The major challenge is their lack of confidence to deliver their instruction in class, which threatens their ability to work independently (Biesta, 2019; Bala, 2017), try new things (Delahajj & Van Dam, 2018), and take risks in the classroom (Chen et al., 2017).

In addition, Flores (2019) elucidated why occupation-focused coping mechanisms are rare in MAPEH. Among these are the need for more control of teachers over their work environment, the large number of students to handle, and the limited resources. Furthermore, Kraft, Blazar, and Hogan D. (2018) explained that non-specialized MAPEH instructors find it challenging to fit in other activities they love since they must spend significant time outside class hours planning courses, marking papers, and attending meetings. Others also feel guilty for taking time for themselves, so they may hesitate to adopt occupation-focused coping techniques because they think their students should focus their whole attention (Darling-Hammond et al., 2019). As a result, burnout burnout and stress are everyday experiences. Thus, Jamaludin and You (2019) recommended that non-specialized teachers utilize well occupation-focused coping strategies to help them manage the strain of their jobs healthily. Subon and Sigie (2018) asserted that striking a balance between their profession and health is the best thing to do, and they suggest scheduling a time for their favorite pastimes and activities that relieve stress.

As observed in the table, emotion-focused obtained the mean of 2.91 (SD=0.67), which means moderate, explicitly denoting that the coping mechanisms in terms of emotion focused of non-specialized teachers are sometimes observed in teaching MAPEH subjects. This outcome was proven by its itemized means, where teachers confessed their maximum tolerance in teaching the subject and the time spent doing things that relax them. Furthermore, some teachers have shown interest in discussing their problems with their families and close circles for stress relief. They prefer to avoid keeping and solving their work burdens by themselves. The result proved how emotionally high these non-specialized teachers were while teaching MAPEH in the class.

The finding contradicts Orlando (2018), who stated that educators who teach subjects in which they do not specialize are highly prone to emotional instability that leads to stress and depression. Bala (2017) asserts that low emotions affect how unmotivated teachers become when teaching the subjects. Such a situation would negatively impact the student's learning process, especially in MAPEH, where teachers are expected to bring positivity and enthusiasm to the class to make the subject fun and engaging. Bilasa (2019) explained that MAPEH is the leading subject that students always look forward to because this is where they can play, mingle more with their classmates, and learn with others through engaging in real-world tasks. Thus, in teaching this course, intense passion, emotion, and motivation are crucial to encouraging students to participate and foster a love for learning (Aguinaldo, 2021; Van den Brande et al., 2019).

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Additionally, Biesta (2019) claims that instructors who utilize coping strategies that are low emotion-oriented become indifferent and are less likely to create a positive and supportive learning environment for their students. Because they are unhappy, they are hesitant to put any effort into organizing or conducting the class. Most of them express negative feelings toward their pupils by becoming impatient and irritated (Orlando, 2018, pp. 29-35). As a result, Co, Abella, and De Jesus (2021, p. 1-13) explain that this kind of classroom setup may hurt how learners perceive learning the material and may increase the likelihood of multiple unfavorable outcomes, including a drop in student motivation and engagement, a spike in behavioral problems, and—most significantly—a decline in student achievement. Thi and Truong (2020) stressed that a MAPEH teacher with a deficient emotion-focused coping mechanism is more likely to experience various types of stress and anxiety, and they are more prone to carry their personal and professional issues into their various lessons by losing their patience or snapping at pupils. As a result, there can be a lousy learning atmosphere, and pupils might feel uneasy, uninspired, and discouraged.

Level of Performance of the Non-Specialized MAPEH Teachers

Table 3. Level of performance of the non-specialized MAPEH teachers, n=150

	\bar{x}	SD
Classroom Management	3.53	0.55
Coaching and Training	2.91	0.83
Handling Ancillary Task	3.59	0.57
Overall	3.34	0.53

Table 3 shows the level of performance of the 150 non-specialized MAPEH teachers in Davao del Sur about classroom management, coaching, teaching, and handling ancillary tasks. As observed, their level of MAPEH performance generally garnered a mean of 3.34 (SD= 0.53), which means moderate, with an implication that the performance of nonspecialized teachers is sometimes observed in teaching MAPEH subjects. This finding underlined that these teachers were often good at managing the class, fulfilling every responsibility that might come even outside their field of work, and teaching the subject matter of each component in MAPEH despite not majoring in this course in their undergraduate years.

Similarly, Datingaling (2019) validated the finding, citing past studies as proof of nonspecialized instructors' competence in teaching MAPEH courses. Ghani, Ahmad, and Ibrahim (2014) uncovered that non-specialist instructors in MAPEH were equally successful at teaching the topic as trained teachers. Similarly, Ferlazzo (2018) emphasized that such instructors have a high degree of knowledge and abilities in teaching MAPEH courses since they have spent years honing their skill sets in areas outside their major. MAPEH is a general subject from elementary to tertiary years. Thus, it is delicate whether specialized instructors can still ideally teach the subject materials under the course (Hershock, 2023).

Guiaselon et al. (2022) also outlined why non-specialized teachers can succeed while instructing MAPEH courses. MAPEH is a vast topic area that includes a range of disciplines, such as music, the arts, physical education, and health. Nixon, Luft, and Ross (2019) indicated that non-specialized teachers are probably familiar with at least one of these topics and have some experience therein. Furthermore, Mizzi (2018) made a similar claim regarding MAPEH as a course that strongly emphasizes practical knowledge and abilities, further suggesting that participation in professional development workshops and conferences can help non-specialized instructors learn how to instruct MAPEH courses successfully. The fact that MAPEH is frequently taught in a collaborative approach illustrated, most crucially, that non-specialized instructors may benefit from and assist one another in the classroom (Ferlazzo, 2018; Ocampo, 2018; Mizzi, 2018).

The result showed in Table 3 that the handling ancillary task of 150 MAPEH teachers in Davao del Sur acquired a mean of 3.59 (SD= 0.57), which means high, expressing that the performance in this aspect of non-specialized teachers is frequently observed in teaching MAPEH subject. Their itemized means suggested that these teachers were highly committed and dedicated. Even when assigned non-teaching-related tasks, they would still perform them and submit such assignments on or before deadlines. They showed a high regard for their profession. Therefore, they always did their best to show outstanding teaching performance.

This finding aligns with Hobbs' postulation (2022), which states that non-specialized MAPEH instructors are open to managing auxiliary duties like dealing with other teachers and planning school activities. Ocampo (2018) stated that these tasks are time-consuming and complex, but instructors have shown that running these events smoothly is still possible while juggling their teaching

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responsibilities. Furthermore, non-specialized MAPEH instructors are frequently driven to take on supplementary duties to support the school community and aid in their students' academic success (Nixon et al., 2019; Mizzi, 2018).

Mangubos (2019) listed recommendations for non-specialized MAPEH teachers to avoid burnout and exhaustion from teaching and ancillary responsibilities. Among these suggestions is the prioritization of tasks, which was reinforced by (Orlando, 2018), who noted that as not all auxiliary jobs are divided evenly, instructors must be aware of these obligations to balance their teaching and non-teaching tasks. Additionally, refusing is okay, especially when teachers are overworked. When carrying out their professional responsibilities both within and outside of their line of work, non-specialized instructors must make sure that their mental and physical health is at their peak (Weldon, 2020, pp. 1-20; Querubin, 2020, pp. 2-9; Waltz, 2016, p. 18- 49).

Regarding classroom management, Table 3 revealed a mean of 3.53 (SD= 0.55), which indicates high, suggesting that the performance in this aspect of non-specialized teachers is frequently observed in teaching MAPEH subjects. This was justified by their itemized means that the participating non-specialized instructors have established rules and regulations in the classroom that clearly explain the repercussions and periodically review these classroom policies to ensure that the students are aware of them. In addition, they encourage students to plan efficiently and offer the most time for specified activities in each MAPEH component during the class session. Such findings conformed to Samillano (2019), who underscored that non-specialist instructors are just as capable of managing their classes as specialized teachers. According to research by Weldon (2020), nonspecialized teachers excelled in classroom management. As Waltz (2016) asserted, classroom management is a skill that can be learned and improved over time. Through professional development programs, workshops, and observation of more seasoned educators, non-specialized instructors can further their learning and application of classroom management.

Furthermore, Aguinaldo (2021) asserted that non-specialized instructors frequently have a good connection with their pupils since they can learn about their unique needs and interests. A good and encouraging learning environment may be produced in the classroom by teachers and students who get along well (Biesta, 2019; Bilasa, 2019). Although they might have less experience instructing MAPEH than specialist instructors, which might make it challenging to become an expert in all its components, Buedron (2018) stated that it does not diminish their capacity to become effective classroom managers. Non-specialized teachers may foster a happy and effective learning environment for their students by learning about classroom management strategies, building strong connections with their learners, and using creativity and resourcefulness (Campbell et al., 2021).

The last indicator for assessing the non-specialized teachers' performance is coaching teaching. Table 3 disclosed a mean of 2.91 (SD= 0.83), which means moderate, implying that the coaching teaching performance of non-specialized teachers is sometimes observed in teaching MAPEH subjects. This was proven by the itemized mean results where teachers confessed their frequency of attending seminars to better their teaching and training for their students. Notably, those teachers who managed student-athletes ensured that training and practice sessions were allotted to better the students' skill set and develop the right attitude towards sports, which they can utilize in competitions. Similar findings were found by Condie, Lefgren, and Sims (2019), who reported that 92% of nonspecialized instructors think coaching is crucial for the success of their students. Additionally, according to Day (2019), college coaches attending professional development seminars are likelier to have successful teams. Darling-Hammond et al. (2019) explained that 85% of non-specialized MAPEH instructors share this belief since training and coaching are necessary for this subject where being hands-on with students is necessary.

Additionally, non-specialized teachers who attend seminars are more likely to employ good teaching techniques and improve their competence because of the expert insights they learn from more knowledgeable teachers in the field (Cohen et al., 2018). Co et al. (2021) affirmed this claim since college coaches who oversee student-athletes always seek methods to enhance their pupils' abilities and attitudes through seminars and advice from their co-coaches. Delahaij and Van Dam (2018) elaborated that seminars may instruct them on cutting-edge teaching techniques and approaches they can utilize in their classrooms. By staying current with the most recent educational research, which may help instructors make informed decisions about their teaching methods (Childs & McNicholl, 2018; Chen et al., 2017; Ghani et al., 2014), teachers can enhance the learning outcomes of their students (Flores, 2019).

Significant Difference of the Coping Mechanisms and Performance of NonSpecialized Teachers as Analyzed by Gender

Table 4. Coping mechanism and performance as analyzed by gender

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum Ranks	Mann- U	Whitne y Z	Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)
Time Management Male	28	80.18	2245	1577	-0.653	0.514
Female	122	74.43	9080			
Total	150					

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Academic Advice	Male	28	76.25	2135	1687	-0.102	0.919
	Female	122	75.33	9190			
	Total	150					
Appraisal Focused	Male	28	86.52	2422.5	1399.5	-1.5	0.134
	Female	122	72.97	8902.5			
	Total	150					
Emotion Focused	Male	28	74.68	2091	1685	-0.111	0.911
	Female	122	75.69	9234			
	Total	150					
Occupation	Male	28	77.5	2170	1652	-0.271	0.786
	Female	122	75.04	9155			
	Total	150					
Coping Mechanism	Male	28	81.04	2269	1553	-0.748	0.455
	Female	122	74.23	9056			
	Total	150					
Classroom Management	Male	28	75.3	2108.5	1702.5	-0.027	0.978
	Female	122	75.55	9216.5			
	Total	150					
Coaching Training	Male	28	66.48	1861.5	1455.5	-1.223	0.221
	Female	122	77.57	9463.5			
	Total	150					
Handling Ancillary Task	Male	28	77.8	2178.5	1643.5	-0.331	0.741
	Female	122	74.97	9146.5			
	Total	150					
Performance	Male	28	70.77	1981.5	1575.5	-0.64	0.522
	Female	122	76.59	9343.5			
	Total	150					

Table 4 presents data using the Mann-Whitney U test for the researchers to determine the coping mechanism and performance of 150 non-specialized MAPEH teachers in Davao del Sur when analyzed by gender. As observed, Table 4 illustrated that overall, there is no significant difference exists in terms of coping mechanisms between males (mean rank = 81.04, Sum of Ranks = 2269) and females (mean rank = 74.23, Sum of Ranks = 9056), $U=1553$, $p= 0.455$. This implied that the non-specialized MAPEH teachers in Davao del Sur, regardless of sex, have similar coping mechanisms in teaching the subject. Hence, this result failed to reject the null hypothesis.

This finding contradicted what Zhou (2018) cited, that female teachers in the US mostly favored and employed the emotion-focused mechanism, which was demonstrated by soliciting assistance and support from their peers to alleviate or, at the very least, release their concerns relating to the subjects they taught. Males, however, were far more problem-focused, leading them to look for solutions on their own to the difficulties and constraints they had to deal with through logical planning and problem-solving. Mangubos (2019) underlined the empirical claims of Orlando (2018), who backed up such a claim, stating that male educators were more logical and reasonable when handling their personal and professional concerns. In contrast, female educators were inclined to share and seek collegial care and counsel.

Nevertheless, Montesur (2021, p. 191-201) found that non-specialized MAPEH instructors in District 4 of Laguna, Philippines, employed comparable coping strategies independent of gender. Teachers' most often applied coping techniques were the best time management, allocation, scheduling practices, academic guidance, and mentorship from seasoned MAPEH instructors in the field. Similarly, in terms of performance, Table 4 revealed that no significant difference was present between males (mean rank = 70.77, Sum of Ranks = 1981.5) and females (mean rank = 76.59, Sum of Ranks = 9343.5), $U=1575.5$, $p= 0.522$. (mean rank = 76.59, Sum of Ranks = 9343.5), $U=1575.5$, $p= 0.522$ This means that the non-specialized MAPEH teachers in Davao del Sur, regardless of sex, have similar performance levels in teaching the subject. Hence, this result failed to reject the null hypothesis.

Parallel to this finding is the claim of Cohen, Ruzek, and Sandios (2018), explaining that both male and female teachers are equally capable of teaching MAPEH effectively. Samillano (2019) stipulated that both teachers participate in training and programs to improve their teaching competence in approaching the various components of MAPEH. Condie, Lefgren, and Sims (2019) stressed

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that such a lack of distinction constitutes positive news for learners as well as instructors because it signifies that the former has a wider variety of competent educators to pick from, and the latter can be confident that they provide excellent instruction irrespective of their gender (Ocampo, 2018; Mizzi, 2018).

Significant Difference in the Coping Mechanisms and Performance of NonSpecialized Teachers as Analyzed by Educational Attainment

Table 5. Coping mechanism and performance as analyzed by Educational Attainment

	Educational Attainment	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann-Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Time Management	Bachelor's Degree	111	77.77	8633	1912	-1.118	0.264
	Master's Degree	39	69.03	2692			
	Total	150					
Academic Advice	Bachelor's Degree	111	76.45	8485.5	2059.5	-0.453	0.651
	Master's Degree	39	72.81	2839.5			
	Total	150					
Appraisal Focused	Bachelor's Degree	111	78.01	8659.5	1885.5	-1.205	0.228
	Master's Degree	39	68.35	2665.5			
	Total	150					
Emotion Focused	Bachelor's Degree	111	75.66	8398.5	2146.5	-0.077	0.938
	Master's Degree	39	75.04	2926.5			
	Total	150					
Occupation	Bachelor's Degree	111	74.7	8291.5	2075.5	-0.383	0.702
	Master's Degree	39	77.78	3033.5			
	Total	150					
Classroom Management	Bachelor's Degree	111	76.67	8510	2035	-0.574	0.566
	Master's Degree	39	72.18	2815			
	Total	150					
Coaching Training	Bachelor's Degree	111	76.32	8471.5	2073.5	-0.392	0.695
	Master's Degree	39	73.17	2853.5			
	Total	150					
Handling Ancillary Task	Bachelor's Degree	111	72.97	8100	1884	-1.277	0.201
	Master's Degree	39	82.69	3225			
	Total	150					
Coping Mechanism	Bachelor's Degree	111	76.55	8497.5	2047.5	-0.501	0.616
	Master's Degree	39	72.5	2827.5			
	Total	150					
Performance	Bachelor's Degree	111	74.77	8300	2084	-0.346	0.73
	Master's Degree	39	77.56	3025			
	Total	150					

Illustrated in Table 5 is the data analysis using the Mann-Whitney U test to show whether significant differences in the coping mechanisms and performance of the 150 nonspecialized MAPEH teachers in Davao del Sur were present when measured by educational attainment. Overall, as seen, there is no significant difference in coping mechanisms between non-specialized teachers with master's degrees (mean rank = 72.5, Sum of ranks = 2827.5) and those with bachelor's degrees (mean = 76.55, Sum of ranks = 8497.5) towards teaching MAPEH subject, Mann-Whitney U (150) = 2047.5, $p=0.616$. Hence, this result failed to reject the null hypothesis.

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This entailed that teachers with either bachelor's or master's degrees have similar coping mechanisms when teaching MAPEH subjects. This finding correlated with Biesta (2019), who claimed that different levels of education needed to be more precise indicators for teachers to utilize different coping strategies to deal with the difficulties of the subjects they taught. Montesur (2021) elucidated that particularly for MAPEH teachers where the subject itself is broad, covering a variety of topics ranging from music, arts, physical education, and health, adopting similar mechanisms is very common to both specialized and nonspecialized MAPEH teachers, like asking collegial advice and mentorship and imitating those pedagogical approaches of the course that were proven to be effective based on the experiences of expert MAPEH teachers in the field (Delahajj & Van Dam, 2018; Chen et al., 2017). Hobb (2022) posited that the challenges of teaching MAPEH do not correlate with the degree of education they achieve since most, if not all, educators encountered difficulties in classroom management, retention of students' motivation towards the course, and assessment of learners' learning. Co, Abella, and De Jesus (2021) underscored that such challenges in teaching MAPEH were unrelated to completed degrees or educational levels.

More so, about teachers' performance, no significant difference was found between nonspecialized teachers with master's degrees (mean rank = 77.56, Sum of ranks = 3025) and those with bachelor's degrees (mean = 74.77, Sum of ranks = 8300) towards teaching MAPEH subject, Mann-Whitney U (150) = 2084, $p = 0.73$. Hence, this result failed to reject the null hypothesis. This explained that educational attainment was not a basis for nonspecialized teachers to be identified as well-performing.

Montesur (2021) supported this finding, revealing that non-specialized MAPEH instructors in District 4 of Laguna, Philippines, showed quality teaching performance despite not majoring in this subject in their undergraduate years. He added a general claim that teachers, by nature, consistently executed the best of their abilities to render quality instruction for the students even if faced with struggles in understanding and teaching the subject matter. Furthermore, Mizzi (2018) identified factors that may affect non-specialized teachers' performance in the academic space. Among them are teaching experiences and motivation, with educational attainment being the least considered when looking at the holistic capability of teachers in terms of pedagogical knowledge. Ferlazzo (2018) contended that not all teachers who proceed to post-degree programs are already competent enough in the field. So do those who do not have masters and doctorates, do not mean that they are not equipped with the proficiency to teach MAPEH. Similarly, Chen et al. (2017) explained that outstanding teaching performance is acquired through various means, such as formal education, experience, and professional exposure. Consequently, educators with various degrees acquire the expertise and knowledge required to become proficient MAPEH instructors (Querubin, 2020; Waltz, 2016).

Significant Difference of the Coping Mechanisms and Performance of NonSpecialized Teachers as Analyzed by Age

Table 6. Coping mechanism and performance as analyzed by age

	Age	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	df	p-value
Time Management	25-34	34	78.71	0.601	3	0.896
	35-34	80	73.52			
	45-44	22	74.45			
	55-64	14	80.68			
	Total	150				
Academic Advice	25-34	34	86.41	3.116	3	0.374
	35-44	80	70.85			
	45-54	22	76.18			
	54-64	14	74.5			
	Total	150				
Appraisal Focused	25-34	34	83.18	3.768	3	0.288
	35-44	80	69.23			
	45-54	22	84.25			
	55-64	14	78.93			
	Total	150				
Emotion Focused	25-34	34	73.35	0.257	3	0.968
	335-44	80	75.53			
	45-54	22	79.27			
	55-64	14	74.61			
	Total	150				
Occupation	25-34	34	85.65	2.999	3	0.392
	35-44	80	71.47			

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	45-54	22	78.61			
	55-64	14	69			
	Total	150				
Classroom Management	25-34	34	80.13	1.762	3	0.623
	35-44	80	71.53			
	45-54	22	77.27			
	55-64	14	84.14			
	Total	150				
Coaching Training	25-34	34	92.21	6.887	3	0.076
	35-44	80	69.63			
	45-54	22	70.23			
	55-64	14	76.79			
	Total	150				
Handling Ancillary Task	25-34	34	79.26	1.388	3	0.708
	35-44	80	74.85			
	45-54	22	68			
	55-64	14	81.86			
	Total	150				
Coping Mechanism	25-34	34	81.94	1.599	3	0.66
	35-44	80	71.68			
	45-54	22	79.93			
	55-64	14	74.71			
	Total	150				
Performance	25-34	34	87.94	4.358	3	0.225
	35-44	80	70.69			
	45-54	22	70.16			
	55-64	14	81.18			
	Total	150				

Table 6 displays the data revealing that overall, there is no significant difference in the nonspecialized teachers' level of coping mechanisms as measured by age groups, Chi-square (3,150) = 1.599, $p = 0.66$. Hence, this result failed to reject the null hypothesis, implying that the 150 non-specialized teachers have similar coping mechanisms in teaching MAPEH subjects even though they are of different ages.

Several types of research have shown that age plays a minor role in how instructors manage the difficulties of teaching MAPEH differently. (Nixon, Luft, & Ross, 2019, p. 1197– 1218; Mizzi, 2018, p. 44–46). Waltz (2016, p. 18-49) reasoned out that the majority, if not all, encountered similar struggles in assessments used to evaluate students learning (Zhou, 2018, pp. 483–497), dealing with and managing MAPEH subjects, ranging from classroom management behavior of the students (Co et al., 2021, pp. 1-13), suitability of and approaches to utilize in MAPEH's different components (Delahaij & Van Dam, 2018, pp. 57-62; Chen et al., 2017, p. 347-363). In addition, in different academic institutions, teachers of all ages are welcome to different learning opportunities and training, mentorship programs, and collaborative planning time that help them grow in the field and provide a better learning experience to their students, thus allowing them to develop or embody similar coping mechanisms appropriate to the challenges they encountered over time (Campbell et al., 2021; Weldon, 2020). For instance, Biesta (2019) and Bilasa (2019) stated that teachers could pick valuable skills, including relying on their peers for help, using the internet to obtain teaching resources, and modifying their teaching strategies to fit the needs and interests of their learners.

In addition, Table 6 revealed that no significant difference was present when nonspecialized MAPEH teachers' teaching performance was analyzed according to their age groups, Chi-square (3,150) = 4.358, $p = 0.225$. Hence, with this result, it failed to reject the null hypothesis. This explained that teachers showed their utmost teaching performance regardless of their age groups. This finding conformed to Montesur (2021), who stipulated that although age determines the scope of experience that teachers have in the teaching profession, there are better criteria to consider when assessing how well a MAPEH teacher performs in the classroom. Similarly, Nixon, Luft, and Ross (2019) highlighted that educators of all ages can effectively teach learning with utmost regard for their skills, knowledge, passion, and motivation. Campbell et al. (2021) explained that every educator has specific talents and flaws. Age is not a factor in evaluating whether a teacher is already competent. Cohen et al. (2017) mentioned that employing and

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supporting educators who are devoted to teaching with passion and assisting students in reaching their potential should be a priority for schools.

Significant Difference in the Coping Mechanisms and Performance of NonSpecialized Teachers as Analyzed by Years in Service

Table 7. Coping mechanism and performance as analyzed by Years in Service

	Year in Service	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	df	p-value
Time Management	1-5 yrs.	23	83.13	1.153	3	0.764
	6-10 yrs.	45	72.68			
	10 yrs. above	82	74.91			
	Total	150				
Academic Advice	1-5 yrs.	23	86.28	2.256	3	0.521
	6-10 yrs.	45	76.42			
	10 yrs. above	82	71.97			
	Total	150				
Appraisal Focused	1-5 yrs.	23	88.28	2.58	3	0.461
	6-10 yrs.	45	71.12			
	10 yrs. above	82	74.32			
	Total	150				
Emotion Focused	1-5 yrs.	23	75.11	1.225	3	0.747
	6-10 yrs.	45	75.63			
	10 yrs. above	82	75.54			
	Total	150				
Occupation	1-5 yrs.	23	89.33	4.953	3	0.175
	6-10 yrs.	45	73.41			
	10 yrs. above	82	72.77			
	Total	150				
Classroom Management	1-5 yrs.	23	82.89	2.62	3	0.454
	6-10 yrs.	45	67.47			
	10 yrs. above	82	77.84			
	Total	150				
Coaching Training	1-5 yrs.	23	89.33	4.263	3	0.234
	6-10 yrs.	45	76.88			
	10 yrs. above	82	70.87			
	Total	150				
Handling Ancillary Task	1-5 yrs.	23	72.83	1.063	3	0.786
	6-10 yrs.	45	75.92			
	10 yrs. above	82	76.02			
	Total	150				
Coping Mechanism	1-5 yrs.	23	84.57	2.236	3	0.525
	6-10 yrs.	45	74.41			
	10 yrs. above	82	73.55			
	Total	150				
Performance	1-5 yrs.	23	84.35	2.107	3	0.551
	6-10 yrs.	45	73.66			
	10 yrs. above	82	74.03			
	Total	150				

In Table 7, the data showed through the Kruskal Wallis test that, overall, there is no significant difference in the non-specialized teachers' level of coping mechanisms as analyzed by their years of service, Chi-square (3,150) = 2.236, p = 0.525. Similarly, their

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teaching performance in MAPEH subjects revealed no significant difference, Chi-square (3,150) = 2.107, $p = 0.551$. Hence, with this result, it failed to reject the null hypothesis. This explained that the 150 MAPEH non-specialized teachers have similar coping mechanisms and performance levels irrespective of their years in the teaching profession.

Jamaludin and You (2019) contradicted this finding, noting that quality teaching is determined by experience. The teaching experience is only assessed by the number of years that the teachers have served in the teaching field. Therefore, those teachers who have been teaching for an extended period have already gained much more experience and exposure than novice teachers, and they still need to acquire those experiences (Flores, 2019). Day (2019) they were stressed that it could not be denied that those who have been serving the teaching industry for many years are well-equipped and are confident to deal with any of them since they might have confronted them in the past years, which also justified their ability to cope with such pressures and stresses at work was higher than others.

This might be true from particular standpoints, but Montesur (2021) argued that in District 4, Laguna, Philippines, non-specialized MAPEH teachers with different years of teaching experience never failed to show excellence. This might be true from particular standpoints, but Montesur (2021) argued that in District 4, Laguna, Philippines, non-specialized MAPEH teachers with different years of teaching experiences never failed to show excellent teaching performance through the positive feedback they obtained from their students. He stated that this happened because teachers were provided with enough training and attended professional development programs to better their teaching skills and become more knowledgeable about subjects they did not major in during their undergraduate years.

Significant Difference in the Coping Mechanisms and Performance of Non Specialized Teachers as Analyzed by Specialization

Table 8. Coping Mechanisms and Performance as analyzed by specialization

	Specialization	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	df	p-value
Time Management	BEED	115	74.01	2.239	4	0.692
	BSED - ENG	13	72.92			
	BSED - FIL	5	76.50			
	BSED - MATH	13	92.04			
	BSED - SCI	4	71.75			
	Total	150				
Academic Advice	BEED	115	78.11	7.493	4	0.112
	BSED - ENG	13	47.08			
	BSED - FIL	5	90.90			
	BSED - MATH	13	80.23			
	BSED - SCI	4	58.25			
	Total	150				
Appraisal Focused	BEED	115	77.05	6.795	4	0.147
	BSED - ENG	13	68.46			
	BSED - FIL	5	64.70			
	BSED - MATH	13	87.73			
	BSED - SCI	4	27.63			
	Total	150				
Emotion Focused	BEED	115	78.18	3.192	4	0.526
	BSED - ENG	13	62.62			
	BSED - FIL	5	77.50			
	BSED - MATH	13	61.19			
	BSED - SCI	4	84.25			
	Total	150				
Occupation	BEED	115	79.54	10.415	4	0.034
	BSED - ENG	13	46.62			
	BSED - FIL	5	100.90			
	BSED - MATH	13	66.46			
	BSED - SCI	4	50.75			
	Total	150				
Classroom Management	BEED	115	77.57	5.995	4	0.200
	BSED - ENG	13	60.00			

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	BSED - FIL	5	106.30			
	BSED - MATH	13	63.12			
	BSED - SCI	4	68.25			
	Total	150				
Coaching Teaching	BEED	115	79.18			
	BSED - ENG	13	48.69			
	BSED - FIL	5	88.00	7.224	4	0.125
	BSED - MATH	13	71.08			
	BSED - SCI	4	55.63			
	Total	150				
Handling Ancillary Task	BEED	115	79.47	49.27		
	BSED - ENG	13				
	BSED - FIL	5	83.70			
	BSED - MATH	13	70.85			
	BSED - SCI	4	51.63	8.169	4	0.086
	Total	150				
Coping Mechanism	BEED	115	78.42			
	BSED - ENG	13	53.08			
	BSED - FIL	5	86.80			
	BSED-MATH	13	75.04	5.520	4	0.238
	BSED - SCI	4	51.75			
	Total	150				
Performance	BEED	115	79.88			
	BSED - ENG	13	46.04			
	BSED - FIL	5	90.60			
	BSED - MATH	13	66.92	9.250	4	0.055
	BSED - SCI	4	54.25			
	Total	150				

According to data from Table 8's Kruskal Wallis test, there is often no discernible difference in the non-specialized teachers' use of coping strategies when their field of expertise is considered; Chi-square (4,150) = 5.520, $p = 0.238$. Additionally, Chi-square (4,150) = 9.250, $p = 0.055$, showed no evidence of a significant difference in their performance in teaching MAPEH courses. As a result, it could not rule out the null hypothesis with this result.

This demonstrated that regardless of their specialization, the 150 MAPEH non-specialized instructors exhibit comparable coping strategies and performance levels.

This finding is supported by Campbell et al. (2021), who claim that non-specialized teachers, when teaching subjects outside of their area of specialization, sought out reliable mentorship from more experienced colleagues to help them navigate the difficulties of teaching a particular subject and ultimately deliver high-quality instruction. Katigba and Andal (2023) discovered similarly that out-of-field physical education teachers with various specializations collectively maintain their self-efficacy to deal with challenges they face when teaching without jeopardizing their capacity to do so. Since they spent years honing their teaching skills, instructors can continue to be effective even when addressing optional courses that have little to do with their elective majors (Abas, 2019; Augusto, 2019). Bayani and Guhao Jr. (2017) highlighted that this reality in the educational sector may be a downside to some. However, from a brighter lens, it is a testament to the versatility of teachers in becoming adaptive and responsive to the needs and demands of the situations.

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Based on the study's findings, the researchers concluded that the non-specialized MAPEH teachers in Davao del Sur showed moderate coping mechanisms and performance as they teach MAPEH subjects. The study revealed that time management and appraisal-focused coping mechanisms are the most common. This showed that most non-specialized MAPEH teachers allocated their time correctly and asked for consultation from their colleagues for better decision-making. It helped them easily cope with the challenges of teaching the subject. Despite the challenges experienced, they managed to carry out their responsibilities as instructors, trainers, and auxiliary task managers. Furthermore, no significant difference was found as their coping mechanisms and performance were analyzed regarding gender, educational attainment, age, and years in service. The findings revealed that regardless of their demographic profile, non-specialized MAPEH teachers could cope with the difficulties of teaching such subjects and perform excellently, just as experienced MAPEH teachers in the field did.

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